

CULTURAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF MEMORIAL MUSEUMS IN PATRIOTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

The study of modern museum practices in Azerbaijan proves that the role of museums in the fields of science, culture, and education is steadily increasing, and their influence on the moral upbringing of the population is growing stronger. This primarily applies to specialized museums, which possess a strong educational potential. However, the role of other museums, such as those dedicated to literature, art, regional studies, and memorials, in this area is also commendable.

Keywords: Memorial museums, Azerbaijani culture, cultural heritage, national memory, patriotism, spiritual enrichment, museum education, historical preservation.

Memorial museums, alongside and in close collaboration with museums representing history, art, literature, and other specialties, reflect our national history and culture. The care and attention given to museum work in Azerbaijan are closely tied to the name of Heydar Aliyev. His contributions to the collection and preservation of the spiritual wealth created by our people over centuries are immense. Since the 1970s, the enrichment of various types of museums in the republic, including memorial museums, has further confirmed these efforts.

Memorial museums in Azerbaijan were established based on the June 1976 decree by the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan SSR and the Council of Ministers of Azerbaijan SSR, titled "On the Perpetuation of the Memory of Great Figures of Literature and Art," as well as the decision of the Ministry of Culture of Azerbaijan SSR from October 31, 1979. The necessity and relevance of creating museums, including memorial museums, are once again affirmed by President Heydar Aliyev's statement: "Azerbaijan has been glorified by great personalities whose memory must be immortalized. Future generations are unaware of their lives and creative works. Various means must be employed in this area."

In the 1970s and 1980s, the memorial museums of prominent figures such as the national poet S. Vurğun, U. Hacıbəyov, writer and public figure N. Narimanov, J. Jabbarli, Bulbul, and H. Javid began operating. During this period of the development of memorial museums, there was a noticeable trend of consecutive museum openings in the capital. It is worth mentioning that some figures had museums established not only in the capital but also in the regions or cities where they were born. For example, Bulbul's house museums were created in both Baku and Shusha, H. Javid's in Baku and Nakhchivan, and S. Vurğun's in Baku and Gazakh.

In the new historical context, memorial museums should evolve into a means of expressing national values and ideals. They should demonstrate the role of national factors and cultural distinctiveness in achieving success in the fields of culture, science, and art.

Museums dedicated to various historical figures, writers, actors, and others can also collect materials related to military-patriotic themes. There is hardly a

writer, dramatist, or publicist whose works do not touch upon military-patriotic topics in one way or another. Therefore, regardless of the museum's profile, special attention should be given to military-patriotic themes in their exhibitions. For example, the letter N. Narimanov wrote to his son Najaf or Jafar Jabbarli's plays such as **Aydin**, **Ogtay Eloğlu**, and **Od Gəlini** (The Bride of Fire), as well as Jalil Mammadguluzadeh's works like **Ölülər** (The Dead), **Dəli Yığıncağı** (Madmen's Gathering), and **Anamın Kitabı** (My Mother's Book), are undoubtedly inspired by these noble values (1, p.39).

The emergence and rapid growth of memorial museums in Azerbaijan, forming an extensive museum network, demonstrates that every nation is inclined to establish and preserve its national culture. Azerbaijan's national-cultural history has produced many significant figures who have contributed to the creation of a contemporary and unique cultural identity. To organize and promote this culture, intellectuals from the fields of science and culture, to some extent, transformed into public and political figures. Individuals like S. Vurğun, U. Hacıbəyov, Niyazi, J. Jabbarli, J. Mammadguluzadeh, M.S. Ordubadi, H. Javid, and Bulbul were not only great poets, playwrights, singers, and composers but also reformers and educators. They sought ways to eliminate the negative conditions in society, such as backwardness, dependence, illiteracy, and outdated traditions, and strived to implement progressive reforms in all aspects of life. These intellectuals were deeply rooted in patriotism and national pride.

Memorial museums have worked to faithfully represent the lives and creative contributions of these prominent figures, delivering comprehensive narratives to their visitors.

It is important to note that when we look at the exhibition collections and the focus of activities of our memorial museums, we see that the creative work of our prominent figures is often presented in a one-sided manner. Their professional achievements are given more attention. For example, Səməd Vurğun is mainly presented as a poet and playwright, Nəriman Nərimanov as a writer-dramatist, Hüseyn Cavid as a writer, Üzeyir Hacıbəyov as the founder of professional Azerbaijani music, and Bulbul as a singer. However,

these distinguished individuals were also public and political figures. Their successes in literature and art were deeply rooted in their political, social, and national activities.

In the past, museum staff tended to remain silent about certain events in the lives of these figures, such as the still-unresolved incidents in Nəriman Nərimanov's life or the reasons behind Hüseyin Cavid's exile to distant Siberia. However, under present conditions, these events are now addressed with courage and a principled stance. The injustices done to these great individuals are openly discussed, and efforts are made to help visitors understand the realities of our nation's struggle for independence.

The current state of memorial museum activities leads to the public and political work of these prominent figures being somewhat overshadowed, hindering the public's full understanding of their contributions. In the present context of freedom of speech in the country, all opportunities exist to address this.

In the current context, where our national independence and statehood are strengthening, our economy is developing, and our culture is being restored and integrated into global culture, the issue of instilling moral-patriotic education among the population has gained even greater importance. Museums can significantly contribute to the study of Azerbaijan's ancient and medieval history. In this regard, when determining the criteria and indicators on which the moral education of the population should be based, the cultural heritage and the exemplary lives and actions of prominent figures in science, culture, and public affairs can serve as foundational elements.

Memorial museums play a crucial role in conveying the exemplary lives of prominent scientific, cultural, and political figures to the public and presenting them as a set of moral guidelines and indicators. The phenomenon of "national cultural heritage" is a continuous process, based on the principle of inheritance, spanning from the deepest layers of a nation's history to the present day. In the formation of this phenomenon, the analysis and emulation of the life and creative achievements of prominent historical figures who belong to the nation hold a significant place.

Memorial museums, which are established to eternalize the memory of various scientific, cultural, and socio-political figures, contribute to preserving and promoting this heritage for future generations.

In the modern era, memorial museums are divided into categories such as museum rooms, museum workshops, house museums, and others (3, p.10). Unlike history museums, which form their collections based on archaeological excavations and ethnographic research, and local history museums, which are dedicated to depicting a region's nature, geography, natural resources, and flora and fauna, memorial museums build their collections around items related to the life and creative work of their subject. These include household items, manuscripts, photographs, portraits, letters resulting from correspondence with various individuals, and archival documents.

Although the methods of operation and sources of exhibits vary, there are common features shared by all museums. Regardless of their specialization, all museums aim to contribute to the moral upbringing of the public (1, p.46).

All museums, in addition to the task of preserving and restoring material cultural artifacts for future generations, play a powerful role as tools of public education and promotion. They bear the responsibility of shaping public opinion in desired directions, depending on the dominant ideology, political orientation, and current socio-political conditions. However, above all, a museum serves as a visual means of inspiring people with new achievements and fostering a belief in their own potential.

It is important to note that when foreign visitors tour museums, they should leave with a sense of respect for the Azerbaijani people, recognizing them as a nation with ancient culture, skill, and power. For local visitors, museums should cultivate love and attachment to their homeland, instilling a rightful pride in the nation's prominent figures and motivating them to make further sacrifices and efforts for their country (4, p.11).

Memorial museums educate visitors based on unique values. The cultural and socio-political figures these museums represent offer crucial examples for raising morally developed individuals (5, p.21).

Currently, regardless of their profile, every museum plays a dual role in society. First, museums are responsible for collecting, restoring, and preserving material cultural artifacts, ensuring they are passed down to future generations. Additionally, by displaying these artifacts, museums fulfill their educational mission. Therefore, the alignment between the exhibitions of Azerbaijani museums, including memorial museums, and their goals is of particular importance (6, p. 24-25).

Memorial museums must actively combat values and morals that are foreign to our national spirit and prevent them from gaining ground in our society. They should also contribute to educating the younger generation with high moral values and a sense of patriotism. Like other institutions focused on ideology and promotion, memorial museums should aim to shape citizens' worldviews based on national mentality and the principles of self-awareness (3, p. 17).

Memorial museums have vast opportunities to introduce the public to the nation's spiritual and cultural heritage, as well as to promote the advantages of living in an independent state. The museums' limitless potential in the field of education and moral development allows them to directly utilize historical changes for their purposes (2, p. 61).

These museums should aim to emphasize the creative, dedicated, and resilient nature of the Azerbaijani people, showcasing the love for their homeland, its hardworking and hospitable population. Through this, they strive to foster a sense of patriotism, inspiring the public to achieve new accomplishments and reinforcing national pride.

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